

The Use and Abuse of Knowledge: Exploring Power, Damnation and Redemption Across Caste and Gender in Girish Karnad's *The Fire and the Rain*

Sudipta Gupta

Assistant Professor, Department of English,
Women's College, Calcutta, India

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Girish Karnad's plays are well connected with ancient Indian myths, legends and folk tales which form an intrinsic and indelible part of our culture. It is in these myths and folk tales that Karnad finds a vehicle of new vision for all the elemental passions and conflicts, and man's eternal struggle for perfection. He sees myths as "a kind of collective historical consciousness that is conveyed through the oral traditions" (Mukherjee, intro 19) His play *The Fire and the Rain*, taken from a story narrated by the saint *Lomash* in the *Vana Parva* of *The Mahabharata* occupies almost a peripheral position within the epic's grand narrative and is also not a very famous one. However, it deals with Vedic rituals and sacrifices and raises extremely pertinent questions about the use and abuse of knowledge and the consequences of such misapplication of knowledge. Besides, it also concerns itself with how knowledge and power are intertwined with one another and how both contribute to the existing power dynamics of societal hierarchies. Karnad focuses on all these important aspects prevalent during the Vedic age while also dealing with the existing caste and gender prejudices. He provides us with an insight into how the right application of knowledge can lead us to the redeeming truth transcending all barriers of caste and gender, while misusing knowledge can bring damnation to the offender and his entire community.

The narrative on which Karnad constructs his play deals with fraternal disharmony which initiates a vicious circle of archetypal human experiences involving passion, loss, anger, betrayal, revenge and transcendence while dealing with Vedic rituals and sacrifices. The original tale focused more on the brahmanical pride associated with knowledge and the feuds of power politics which bear an unmistakable stamp of masculinity. Karnad "re-interprets and re-presents the myth" (Jayalakshmi, 261) and reconstitutes it by introducing Nittilai, a tribal young girl who does not have a counterpart in the epic narrative, to problematize the questions of knowledge and power through the aspects of caste and gender. The character of Nittilai complicates the narrative by raising immensely relevant questions associated with the welfare of the entire community thereby providing a new dimension to the ancient power politics. Apart from this, through the characters of Nittilai, and Arvasu, the Brahmin youth who later becomes

an outcaste, Karnad provides a glimpse into the reality of the Vedic truth which can be pursued with honesty and integrity and not with hubristic pride and caste prejudice.

In the words of R.K. Dhawan, “Karnad goes back to myths and legends with a view to making them a vehicle of a new vision.” (Dhawan, 15) Through this myth of the sages Raibhya and Bharadwaj and their sons Parvasu and Yavakri, Karnad warns the readers about the dangers of false knowledge and the deadly fires of the seven sins. Yavakri, sage Bharadwaj's son acquires knowledge of the Vedas from Indra but that does not stop him from seducing his sister-in-law Vishakha, his former beloved who is now Parvasu's wife. There was a draught for ten long years and Parvasu, the elder son of sage Raibhya was chosen as the chief priest of the fire sacrifice, who would invoke the rain god and bring forth rain in this parched land and restore it to its former state. The fire sacrifice was a Vedic ritual and Parvasu's sound knowledge of the Vedas made him the uncontested person most suitable as the chief priest and the saviour of the people. Yavakri chooses to humiliate his cousin Parvasu's wife not out of any sort of amorous motive, but to revenge his failure to be the chief priest, turning the personal into the political. Hence, we find that none of the learned men are concerned about the welfare of the community, both want to be the chief priest only to gain a position of power and hence prove the superiority of his knowledge over the other's. As Yavakri tells Vishakha: “My father deserved to be invited as the Chief Priest of the sacrifice. But that too went to Parvasu, your husband. Even in the midst of my austerities I wept when I heard the news.” (Karnad, 130) As a result of his sinful deed, Yavakri is killed by the demon spirit created by sage Raibhya, the *brahmarakshasha*. On the other hand, the chief priest Parvasu becomes guilty of patricide and brahminicide when he intentionally kills his father sage Raibhya in a fit of rage to be even with each other. We find that there is no existence of the usual paternal and filial bond between this father son duo. Raibhya sees Parvasu as his competitor for being the chief priest to whom he lost and Parvasu accuses his father directly: “He killed Yavakri to disturb me in the last stages of the sacrifice... I had to attend to him before he went any further.” (Karnad, 142) Parvasu, who considers himself unparalleled in Vedic knowledge and rituals, continues the fire sacrifice with the blood of patricide on his hands and finally immolates himself in a situation of utter chaos when he realizes he would not be able to complete the sacrifice, abandoning the villagers without any hope of rains. Both Yavakri and Parvasu refuse to use their knowledge for benevolent purposes; rather they misuse knowledge for their own selfish ends which leads the entire community towards damnation and destruction. They embody the fires of lust, greed, anger, envy and revenge within themselves and are ultimately destroyed by the all-consuming flames of their own sins.

Yavakri and Parvasu become almost mirror images of one another not only in their misapplication of knowledge but also in the boastful remarks that they make about themselves. When Yavakri describes his search of universal knowledge to Vishakha, his words are reeling with pride and completely devoid of any kind of humility: “You go into the jungle. You perform austerities in the name of some god. You stand in a circle of fire. The pressure of your austerities forces the god to grant you your wish. And you get ‘Universal knowledge.’ Victory!” (Karnad, 119) Knowledge is not a virtue here, but an instrument of proving oneself superior to others in the game of power politics, a weapon that can be wielded as and when

necessary to settle personal scores: “The past isn’t gone. It’s here inside me. The time has come to show the world what my father’s son is capable of.” (Karnad, 130) Hence, right action does not follow from knowledge and virtue; rather knowledge is abused and misapplied almost in a Faustian manner leading to self damnation. Again, Yavakri seducing Vishakha is an example of knowledge without redemption. Imprisoned within the fires of jealousy, Yavakri sees her only as an instrument of revenge in this wretched game of power politics. He may have gained infinite knowledge as he boastfully proclaims to his former beloved; however his knowledge has not led him to any self realization and hence he has failed to control his inner demons. Almost in a similar vein, Paravasu wanted immortality, to be equal with the Gods and sees the fire sacrifice or the yagna as nothing more than a structured ritual and as a means of achieving name, fame and glory. He confesses to his wife Vishakha:

“I went because the fire sacrifice is a formal rite. Structured. It involves no emotional acrobatics from the participants. The process itself shall bring Indra to me. And if anything goes wrong, there’s nothing the gods can do about it. It has to be set right by a man. By me. That’s why when the moment comes I shall confront Indra in silence. As an equal.” (Karnad, 141)

It is the personal which is placed higher than the collective and hence Paravasu is not involved emotionally and spiritually with either the people or the yagna. This is supremely ironic as the responsibility of the entire community is shouldered by the chief priest as he appeals to the gods through the sacrificial yagna. He suffers from classic hubris and lacks the spiritual discipline expected from the chief priest. Besides, he is an extremely caste conscious man who is too proud of his Brahmin identity with absolutely no regard for the cultural codes of other castes. Karnad exposes him as an extremely power hungry and selfish man, who does not hesitate to mistreat his wife Vishakha or murder his own father, the sage Raibhya or even put the blame of patricide and brahminicide on his innocent younger brother Arvasu only to hold on to the position of the chief priest. He is arrogant enough to consider himself as the saviour of the people, as the chief priest of the fire sacrifice even after murdering his father consciously and intentionally. He covets the position of the chief priest as it involves immense power, but does not acknowledge the responsibility which is associated with that power. All his learning and knowledge have failed to make him wise or humble and is incapable to free him of the seven deadly sins. Hence when it is utter chaos within the sacrificial arena and the chief priest has to make a decision on behalf of the entire community, Paravasu abandons everyone in the midst of all the cacophony and immolates himself in the fire. Since he is the chief priest, he does not think it necessary at all to render an explanation or an apology to the people; rather it adds to his arrogance that he can decide the exact moment of his death, leaving behind an entire community in utter despair. It is the lack of spirituality and humanity coupled with the application of knowledge without wisdom which render Yavakri’s and Paravasu’s search for the eternal truth futile as they lack the inner perspicacity to comprehend the Vedas in their true values. Besides, both of them are imprisoned within their own dark chambers of the seven deadly sins, which render them incapable of redemption, both in the private world as well as in the collective world.

“In a radical move, Karnad invents the parallel story of Arvasu’s relationship with the tribal young girl Nittilai, and develops Arvasu as the antithesis to Raibhya, Parvasu and Yavakri.” (Karnad, intro, xviii) Right from the beginning of the play, Karnad foregrounds the fact that Arvasu, the younger son of sage Raibhya is completely different from his father, elder brother as well as his cousin Yavakri. Instead of following their footsteps and immersing himself in the search for knowledge, Arvasu is more interested in learning the intricate details of acting and theatrical performances. He respects his elder brother but acknowledges the differences between them in his declarations: “I’ll never be learned like father or uncle. I shan’t ever conduct the royal sacrifice like Parvasu or perform penance like cousin Yavakri.” (Karnad, 11). Though acting and theatrical performances complemented Vedic rituals, it was strictly prohibited for brahmins as it was a profession particular only to the members of the shudra caste. Arvasu’s inclination towards the performing arts is perhaps the reason which makes him fall in love with Nittilai, the tribal young girl. The character of Arvasu becomes a binary counterpoint to the brahminism and asceticism of the other male characters, replacing their spiritual sterility with instinct and emotion. He becomes the connecting link between the brahmin and the shudra worlds reflected in his unquestionable admiration for his elder brother and his unrelenting love for Nittilai, exposing their explicit oppositions. On the other hand, Nittilai is presented as a woman who embodies within herself the very fragrance of nature and the forbearance of mother earth. She knows the forest inside out, is conversant with the flora and fauna of her land and prioritises the welfare of the community more than anything else. It is evident in her pertinent question which interrogates Yavakri’s individual ethics in times of a community crisis: “My point is since Lord Indra appeared to Yavakri and Indra is their God of Rains, why didn’t Yavakri ask for a couple of good showers?” (Karnad, 116) This should have been the primary concern of Yavakri; however he is too busy settling personal scores than to think about the welfare of his community whereas a simple tribal girl like Nittilai with no serious knowledge of the scriptures comes up with this appropriate question as she places community welfare before her own interests. After Parvasu betrays Arvasu as the one guilty of patricide and brahminicide and equates him to a demon out there to destroy the sacred fire sacrifice, he is beaten up severely as a punishment for his sins. Besides, he is also treated as an outcaste and ostracized from the brahmin community. As he lies alone suffering from his wounds, the low caste manager of an actors’ group finds him and Nittilai, who runs away from her own husband, saves his life and nurses him back to health. There is unmistakable irony in the fact that the erstwhile brahmin man becomes an outcaste, loses his twice born status only to find shelter among those people whom he had always admired and wanted to spend time with had not his upper caste come in the way.

It is the fire sacrifice which becomes the central metaphor of both the individual and the society where Karnad explores knowledge and its application without wisdom leading to spiritual destruction. Here, myths become integrated to the primitive religious narratives with the quest for knowledge, absence of true spirituality, fraternal disharmony and social customs. In the words of Nayak, the play “presents a fire analysis of human psyche” (Nayak, 233) with the fire representing the flames of lust, jealousy, pride and revenge without any of the purifying or Promethean qualities associated with the fire of Vedic rituals, the yagna. Again, it is at this

sacrificial altar where the climax of the play unfolds exposing the opposition between brahmin and shudra, blind ritual and compassionate faith, spiritual emptiness and altruistic hope where the final redemption takes place, transcending the societal barriers of caste and gender.

The play- within a- play refuses to be only a framing device but also an intrinsic part of the thematic action as it blurs the differences between fact and fiction, between the sacrifice and the performance. All demarcations between fact, fiction and performance erase out, the real and the stage persona merge into one illusion with the question of ethical choices and the final act of redemption. The two brothers face each other, Parvasu in his respected position of the chief priest and Arvasu, in the disguise of a low born actor. The tale of the two brothers Vritra and Vishwaroopa resembles both the grand narrative of *The Mahabharata* as well as this sub narrative of the *Vana parva* in its theme of fraternal strife and feud for knowledge, superiority and power. The actor- manager had warned Arvasu to keep a tight control over the mask: “Once you bring a mask to life you have to keep tight control over it, otherwise it’ll try to take over.” (Karnad, 165) The moment when Indra attacks Vishwaroopa treacherously in this play- within- a play, the mask of Vritra which Arvasu wears for the performance overpowers him where his real self and the role he is playing merge with each other completely. The assumed self becomes Arvasu’s real self temporarily and his mask comes alive, replacing fraternal obedience by the reality of fraternal disharmony which “acquires a transgressive and subversive function.” (Nair, 151) As Arvasu runs towards the real sacrificial altar, this metatheatrical device becomes the medium of catching the conscience of Parvasu leading to his self immolation abandoning the sacrificial altar. On the other hand, “Arvasu’s rampaging action as Vritra at the end of the play is reflective of his anguish and anger and makes him an agent of retributive justice” (Jayalaksmi, 259) while Nittilai gets killed by her own brother for betraying her husband.

It is Nittilai, who does not have a counterpart in the epical grand narrative, and Arvasu, who becomes a Brahmin outcaste living with the sin of patricide as the albatross round his neck, who bring about the much needed rains, which has the power to redeem the villagers. None of them are learned in the conventional sense, none have the traditional knowledge required to preside over Vedic rituals, yet it is them who pursue the truth with honest and pure hearts and finally lift the curse of draught from this parched land. Karnad debunks the traditional caste hierarchies and social customs and convictions, exposing the hypocrisies prevalent in the then society where the final redemptive moment for the greatest happiness of the greatest number is reached only when the caste, gender and ritual barriers are transcended. It is this blessed duo, who stand for the welfare of the entire community when there is absolutely no one to preside over the fire sacrifice, no one to decide the Vedic customs and no one to lead the hapless and hopeless villagers. Karnad shows the true power of knowledge and learning which can lead one to damnation if misused and misapplied only for selfish and narrow ends and can also lead one to redemption when used with wisdom for the greatest good of the greatest number of people; which the Rigveda calls “*bahujana hitāya bahujana sukhāya ca.*”

Indian philosophy speaks of the choice from a set of one’s obligations of one’s varna and ashrama- the moral dilemma of prioritizing one’s obligations; “to weigh the options and

decide what is the right course of action” (Srivastava and Boruah 85) It is to Arvasu, the ostracized Brahmin youth and a complete binary to his brother to whom Lord Indra appears and offers a choice: he could either bring Nittilai back to life or liberate the *brahmarakshasa* from the shackles of the life cycle. The final redemptive act of the play is neither the yagna nor the performance but the ethical choice of Arvasu to release the *brahmarakshasa* from the vicious cycle of life and death than to gain his own happiness by bringing Nittilai back to life again. It is Arvasu who had an intrinsic knowledge of humanity uncontaminated by the fires of the seven deadly sins for which he could comprehend the essence of the Vedic mantras and sacrifice the personal for the community. He prioritises the community over the individual and sacrifices his beloved for the multitude, comprehending the mantra of the Rigveda in its entirety, leading to the liberation of the draught stricken land from the ten year curse which can be seen as the “revelatory epiphany.” (Jayalaksmi, 251) Parvasu becomes an immediate binary to his younger brother, whose actions steer the next course of action after his self immolation revealing all his knowledge as dry and rusty, devoid of any kind of humanity and spirituality. Karnad points out the supreme irony as he exposes all the pretensions and hypocrisies, all the vain arrogance and boastful pride associated with masculine caste supremacy through the character of Nittilai. Nittilai, the tribal young girl, for whom even entering the sacrificial arena of the yagna is prohibited, Nittilai, who is twice marginalized as the other both in the caste and gender hierarchies, Nittilai, who pays with her life for being a transgressor, becomes almost like a female Christ who brings in restoration, rejuvenation, regeneration and redemption without resurrection and who suffers a terrible death only for the sake of the collective. While the two arrogant men Yavakri and Parvasu are consumed by the flames of the destructive fire within them, it is the so-called prohibited ones who are purified by the sacrificial fires of the yagna to which they are denied access due to their caste and gender. It is Arvasu and Nittilai who are blessed with the Promethean qualities of this sacred fire which provide them with the potential of redemption. They are merciful and can forgive and live (or die) for the greater good of the collective. Hence, almost as a fitting conclusion, they become synonymous with the rain of the title of the play quenching all the deadly fires of lust, revenge, anger, greed, pride and jealousy and leading the cursed land towards redemption; all the while reminding us of Portia's famous lines: “The quality of mercy is not strain'd, / It droppeth as the gentle rain from heaven / Upon the place beneath:” (Shakespeare, 111)

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